

Reactivity of Conjugated Systems. Part I. Condensation of Acetylenic Ketones with Cyanoacetamide.

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In Part I of this series (Barat, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 321), it was shown that in conjugated systems of the type $R \cdot CH=CH \cdot CR' = O$, the ethylenic linkage possesses a greater activity with regard to a reactive methylene group than the ketonic group. In the present work, the reaction between conjugated systems of the type $R \cdot C \equiv C \cdot CR' = O$ and cyanoacetamide has been studied mainly with the object of establishing the identities of certain 4:6-substituted pyridone derivatives obtained in the course of the previous work, both with Michael's and Knoevenagel's reagents.

By condensing benzoylphenylacetylene with malonic ester, Kohler obtained α -pyrone derivatives which he converted into the corresponding hydroxypyridine by the action of ammonia (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 379). Michael had observed before him (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1894, ii, 49, 22) that malonic ester also condenses with esters of acetylenic acids, and quite recently, Bardhan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, p. 2223) has recorded the condensation of propionylphenylacetylene with cyanoacetamide. But he has not proceeded further than distinguishing this condensation product from the one obtained from propionylacetophenone and cyanoacetamide.

Mourseau (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1905, iii, 33, 131) and his collaborators have established beyond doubt that the triple-bond in these ketones is far more reactive than the ethylenic double bond in the corresponding arylidene ketones, and so it is quite justifiable to conclude that the primary addition of cyanoacetamide must take place at the triple-bond forming a compound of the type (I), which, by virtue of the great tendency of formation of a pyridine ring, immediately suffers ring-closure yielding a cyanopyridone of the type (III), which on

hydrolysis gives a hydroxypyridine (IV) identical with that obtained from the corresponding arylidene ketones (*loc. cit.*).

It is distinctive to note that neither the open-chain amide (I) nor the aldol compound (II) has been isolated under the experimental conditions even in the presence of Knoevenagel's reagent, whilst, with arylidene ketones the intermediate aldol type is readily isolable (*cf.* Barat, *loc. cit.*, also Kohler, *loc. cit.*). This has been no doubt due to the extreme tendency of the formation of a pyridine compound, which precludes the isolation of any intermediate aldol derivative. This phenomenon further supports the similarity of Michael's and Knoevenagel's reactions, first postulated by Sen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1347).

That the original condensation product belongs to type (IV) (at least in presence of alkali) has been proved by its readily yielding an *N*-methyl derivative, identical with the product derived from cyanoacetmethylamide and the corresponding ketones. The absence of a hydroxyl group is rendered extremely probable by its failure to give any colour reaction with alcoholic ferric chloride. Its solubility in alkalis, in the absence of a hydroxyl group, further indicates the presence of an imido-group. The hydrolysed product (V), however, does not yield a methyl derivative readily and exhibits a characteristic colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride, indicating the presence of a hydroxyl group and the absence of an imido-group, and in consequence the structure (V) has been ascribed to it.

It must, however, be admitted that there is a great likelihood of the addition product (I) being converted into (V) through the

intermediary of a compound of type (VI) formed by intramolecular rearrangement, on account of the greater stability of the type (VI) than type (I) in such three-carbon systems (cf. Lapworth and McRae, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2747; Kon and his collaborators, *ibid.*, 1928, 128, 1961, and subsequent papers; also Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 481).

(VI)

It is evident therefrom that the type (VI) can exist as long as the cyano-group is intact. On its hydrolysis, however, intramolecular rearrangement may be assumed to give rise to the hydroxy configuration (V).

Nevertheless it is equally true that the system (III $\rightleftharpoons$ IV) is a tautomeric one, and as such it is difficult to ascribe any particular constitution to the substance. In the present work therefore, these compounds have been described as 4:6-disubstituted-3-cyano-2-pyridones in the general sense.

During the course of the present work, cyanoacetamide has been condensed with (1) benzoylphenylacetylene, (2) *p*-toluylphenylacetylene, (3) *p*-nitrobenzoylphenylacetylene, (4) acetylphenylacetylene, and (5) propionylphenylacetylene, with the additional object of examining the stability of the condensation products in relation to the substituent groups. It has been observed that whether with Michael's or Knoevenagel's reagents, identical products are obtained under both conditions.

It has been of great interest to observe that while the reaction proceeded with remarkable ease in the former cases giving excellent yields of the products, the yields were extremely low with the two latter ketones. (Quite an analogous phenomenon was also noticed in the case of cyanoacetamide condensations with arylidene ketones, *loc. cit.*). Evidently therefore the stability of the condensation products increases with increasing negative character of R in (IV). This fact could be explained by an extension of Fry's substitution rule for benzene derivatives (Fry, "The Electronic Conception of Valence and the Constitution of Benzene," 1921) to the pyridine rings considered herein.—an idea which does not appear to have been applied to pyridine derivatives before (cf. Fry, *J. Amer.*

Chem. Soc., 1912, **34**, 664, *et seq*; also *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1911, **76**, 885, *et seq*).

In the pyridine skeleton (VII) since the NH-group is acidic in nature, giving rise to stable alkali salts, the nitrogen atom in position (1) must be negative to start with. Taking this to be the "key atom" (*cf.* Lapworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, **79**, 1265; *Proc.*, 1901, **17**, 93; *Mem. Manchester Phil. Soc.*, 1920, *ii*, **64**, 1; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 416; also Burokhardt and Lapworth, *ibid.*, 1925, **127**, 1742) and starting along the order indicated in (VII) it will be found that the C atoms (4) and (6) are of a *positive* nature, and hence can form stabler combinations with *negative* substituents. Further, when the carbon atom (4) is already attached to a phenyl (negative) group, it will favour a similar combination (with a negative group) with the carbon atom (6) (*i.e.*, *meta* to it). This also is quite in a line with Fry's substitution rule for benzene derivatives, *viz.*, "when the substituents are of the same sign or polarity, they will occupy positions which are *meta* to each other....." (Stewart, "Recent Advances in Organic Chemistry", 1927, Vol. I, p. 343).

On these considerations it would be quite reasonable to expect that the condensation product (IV) would be more stably constituted when R is a phenyl, tolyl or *p*-nitrophenyl group than when it is a methyl or ethyl group, and this expectation has been borne out by facts.

It is further of interest to observe that the hydrolysis of the cyano-group in (IV) takes place with very nearly quantitative yields when R is phenyl, tolyl or *p*-nitrophenyl, while the yield is comparatively poor when R is methyl or ethyl. This further proves the greater stability of the 6-aryl derivatives.

These compounds have been found to be identical with the dehydrogenation products of the tetrahydropyridone derivatives

obtained by condensing cyanoacetamide with the corresponding arylidene ketones (*loc. cit.*).

Another point worthy of note has been the identity of the cyano-pyridone obtained from acetylphenylacetylene, with the Knoevenagel condensation product between cyanoacetamide and benzalacetone obtained by Sen (*loc. cit.*). Sen's compound, as observed by him, contained two atoms of hydrogen less than required by theory, and was therefore the dehydrogenated product, formed no doubt by the prolonged action of diethylamine on the original condensation product by a process of reciprocal oxidation and reduction,—a phenomenon which these bodies exhibit in presence of alcoholic ammonia (*cf. Barat, loc. cit.*, also Kohler and Souther, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 2903.).

The present work, together with the former of the series, thus clearly points to the reactivity of the unsaturated centres in conjugated systems, to which theory additional experimental evidence will be brought forward in subsequent communications.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Considerable difficulty had to be experienced in the preparation of these ketones, on account of the tedious methods as well as the comparatively low yields. The acylphenylacetylenes were prepared by the general method of Nef (*Annalen*, 1899, 308, 264), while phenylacetylene was prepared according to the method of Hessler ("Organic Synthesis", Vol. II, p. 67).

General Methods.—The condensations were carried out, both by Michael's as well as Knoevenagel's method in an exactly similar manner to those employed in the case of arylidene ketones (*Barat, loc. cit.*, p. 828) with the only exception that in the case of Michael's reaction the temperature was kept low, as otherwise tar formation, owing to secondary reactions, ensued. On mixing the ketone with the pasty sodiocyanoacetamide, the colour became intense red, and the solid went gradually into solution; the colour, however, became lighter as the reaction proceeded, resulting in the separation of the sodium derivative of the condensation product. This was collected usually after one day. The sodium salt was washed with cold alcohol, taken up with water, and decomposed by dilute mineral acids. It could then be separated, washed with water, dried and purified by crystallisation. The mother-liquor, on

dilution and acidulation, gave a further quantity of the substance, hardly profitable to recover on account of the small quantity obtained, as well as the impurities that are difficult to remove. The Knoevenagel's reaction was usually finished in three or four days, but the mixture was handled after a week; the solid that separated out by itself was usually taken, the mother-liquor generally yielding very impure products which contained appreciable quantities of the corresponding β -diketone, formed by the action of water on the acetylenic ketone. These cyanopyridones were identical with those obtained from the corresponding arylidene ketones, and yielded *N*-methyl derivatives when left over at ordinary temperature with an equivalent of sodium methoxide and an excess of methyl iodide in methyl alcoholic solution, till the mixture became neutral. The conversion was usually finished in a day or two and the product was isolated by evaporating the mixture on the water-bath, washing the residue with water till free from iodides, followed by crystallisation of the solid that remained behind. The same product was also obtained when the sodium salt obtained from the Michael's reaction was similarly treated with methyl iodide. An identical compound was also obtained when the corresponding ketone was condensed with cyanoacetmethylamide by Michael's method; the product so obtained was no longer soluble in alkalis, and hence could be separated merely by dilution of the reaction mixture and extracting with chloroform or ether. The reaction, however, was slower in this case and the mixture did not deposit any sodium derivative. The solution was then evaporated to dryness and the residue crystallised.

The cyanopyridones could be hydrolysed by heating with 75-80% sulphuric acid in the usual way. These bodies were identified with specimens from stock and were also identical with specimens prepared by other ways (cf. Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 481).

Benzoylphenylacetylene and Cyanoacetamide.

The ketone was prepared by the method of Nef; it was a deep yellow heavy oil boiling between 190° and 200° at 15-18 mm. (yield about 60%).

3-Cyano-4:6-diphenyl-2-pyridone (IV, R = *Phenyl*).—The substance was obtained in an yield of about 75% by Michael's method. It was very sparingly soluble in all solvents excepting glacial acetic acid and pyridine; crystallised from glacial acetic acid it melted at 320°.

and was identical with the dehydrogenated product of the Michael's condensation product from benzalacetophenone and cyanacetamide. It was soluble in moderately dilute alkalis, but not so in concentrated solutions, on account of the sparing solubility of the sodium salt. On much dilution the solution became turbid owing to the hydrolysis of the salt. It gave no colouration with ferric chloride. With Knoevenagel's reagent (diethylamine or piperidine) an identical compound was obtained in a yield of about 40-50%. (Found: N, 10.08. $C_{18}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 10.30 per cent.).

The *N*-methyl derivative obtained as usual was no longer soluble in alkalis, neither did it give any colouration with ferric chloride. It was very soluble in all common organic solvents excepting petroleum ether; crystallised from rectified spirit it was obtained in small colourless prisms, m.p. 175°. (Found: N, 9.85. $C_{19}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 9.78 per cent.). An identical compound was obtained by condensing the ketone with cyanacetmethylamide.

Hydrolysis of (IV): Formation of 4:6-Diphenyl-2-hydroxypyridine (V, R=Phenyl).—It was isolated by diluting the sulphuric acid solution (yield, 80%). On filtering and washing it free from acids it was crystallised from rectified spirit in fine yellowish-white needles, m.p. 208°. It was identified with other samples of the substance in hand. (Found: N, 5.63. $O_{17}H_{13}ON$ requires N, 5.66 per cent.).

p-Toluyphenylacetylene and Cyanoacetamide.

The ketone was prepared by the action of *p*-toluyl chloride on the sodium salt of phenylacetylene in an exactly similar way as in the previous case (yield, 60%). The *p*-toluyl chloride was prepared by the action of thionyl chloride on *p*-toluic acid (yield, 85.87%). *p*-Toluyphenylacetylene was obtained as a heavy yellow oil, b.p. 200-10°/15 mm. It solidified on cooling and was very soluble in all organic solvents excepting petroleum ether, and crystallised from rectified spirit in large yellowish prisms, m.p. 72°. (Found: C, 86.98; H, 5.83. $C_{16}H_{12}O$ requires C, 87.27; H, 5.45 per cent.).

3-Cyano-4-phenyl-6-p-tolyl-2-pyridone (IV, R=p-Tolyl).—The mixture became intense red on mixing and sodiocyanoacetamide went into solution on shaking; soon afterwards the mixture set to a solid mass and the colour faded down to a faint pink. The sodium salt was separated, and the free product isolated therefrom as usual (yield, about 78%). Crystallised from glacial acetic acid it was obtained as cream-coloured prismatic needles, m.p. 268°.

It was identical with a specimen of the cyanopyridone obtained from benzal-*p*-methylacetophenone and cyanoacetamide as also with another sample obtained by condensing α -methoxy- ω -*p*-toluylstyrene with cyanoacetamide (Basu, *private communication*). It resembled its lower homologue in all its physical and chemical properties. (Found: N, 9.89. $C_{19}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 9.78 per cent.).

The *N*-methyl derivative obtained as usual, crystallised from methyl alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 136-38°. (Found: N, 9.57. $C_{20}H_{16}ON_2$ requires N, 9.33 per cent.). It was identified with a sample obtained by condensing the ketone with cyanoacetmethylamide.

Hydrolysis of the Compound: Formation of 4-Phenyl-6-p-tolyl-2-hydroxypyridine (V, R=*p*-Tolyl).—The hydroxypyridine was obtained in an yield of about 80% when the above condensation product was hydrolysed with 75% sulphuric acid in the usual way. It resembled its lower homologue in all its properties, both physical and chemical. It crystallised from rectified spirit in fine yellowish needles, m.p. 228°. It was identified with a specimen from stock by the method of mixed melting points. (Found: N, 5.53. $C_{18}H_{15}ON$ requires N, 5.36 per cent.).

p-Toluylyphenylacetylene and Ethyl Malonate.

Formation of Ethyl 4-Phenyl-6-p-tolyl-2-pyrone-3-carboxylate.—The condensation was carried out by the method of Kohler (*loc. cit.*) by adding a trace of sodium ethoxide to a hot alcoholic solution of equivalent quantities of the ketone and the ester. The product was isolated on the next day by acidulating with acetic acid (yield, about 70%). The mother-liquor gave some more impure product which was rejected. It had all the properties attributed to its lower homologue by Kohler. It crystallised from methyl alcohol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 85°. (Found: C, 75.29; H, 5.56. $C_{21}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 75.45; H, 5.39 per cent.).

The free pyrone (*4-phenyl-6-p-tolyl-2-pyrone*) was directly obtained when the above ester was taken up with an excess of sodium ethoxide in alcoholic suspension, and left over till the red colour that first developed, completely disappeared (usually 3 to 4 days). Some of the pyrone separated and the rest could be isolated on dilution of the mother-liquor; crystallised from alcohol it was obtained in thin flakes, m.p. 133°, (decomp.) (yield about 65%). (Found: C, 82.25; H, 5.61. $C_{18}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 82.44; H, 5.34 per cent.).

p-Nitrobenzoylphenylacetylene and Cyanoacetamide.

p-Nitrobenzoylphenylacetylene was prepared by the action of *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride on sodium phenylacetylene in the usual way. The chloride was prepared by treating *p*-nitrobenzoic acid with thionyl chloride. The ketone, a solid, separated out on the addition of water to the ethereal reaction mixture, and was moderately soluble in ether, alcohol and benzene. Crystallised from acetone it was obtained in light, golden-yellow flakes, m.p. 161-62°. (Found: N, 5.67. $C_{15}H_9O_3N$ requires N, 5.58 per cent.).

3-Cyano-4-phenyl-6-*p*-nitrophenyl-2-pyridone (IV, R=*p*-Nitrophenyl).—The mixture became red as usual and the condensation was over very soon, resulting in the fading out of the colour to pale brownish-yellow. The product was isolated as usual (yield about 75 %). It was very sparingly soluble in all other solvents excepting pyridine and glacial acetic acid. Crystallised from pyridine diluted with a few drops of alcohol it was obtained in small canary-yellow felty needles melting at 332-33°. It resembled the other members of the series in its properties. (Found: N, 13.20. $C_{18}H_{11}O_3N_3$ requires N, 13.25 per cent.).

The *N*-methyl derivative crystallised from a mixture of amyl alcohol and pyridine (equal volumes); m.p. 322-24°. (Found: N, 12.59. $C_{19}H_{13}O_3N_3$ requires N, 12.69 per cent.).

Hydrolysis of the above Cyanopyridone: Formation of 4-Phenyl-6-p-nitrophenyl-2-hydroxypyridine (V, R=*p*-Nitrophenyl).—The cyanopyridone was more resistant towards hydrolysis than the preceding analogous compounds. It could however be hydrolysed by 80% sulphuric acid or fuming hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube (at 180-200° for 6 to 8 hours). The hydrolysis product was soluble in alkalis and gave a characteristic brown coloration with ferric chloride and resembled the other hydroxypyridines in its properties. Crystallised from dilute acetic acid it was obtained in yellow needles that melted at 275-76°. (Found: N, 9.45. $C_{17}H_{13}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9.60 per cent.).

p-Nitrobenzoylphenylacetylene and Ethyl Malonate.

Formation of Ethyl 4-Phenyl-6-p-nitrophenyl-2-pyrone-3-carboxylate.—The condensation was carried out, and the product separated,

in the usual manner. It crystallised from alcohol in dull yellow needles, m.p. 148°. (Found: N, 4.01. $C_{20}H_{15}O_6N$ requires N, 3.84 per cent.). When hydrolysed with sodium methoxide in methyl alcoholic solution in the cold it gave rise to 4-phenyl-6-p-nitrophenyl-2-pyrone, that crystallised from acetic acid in light yellow needles and melted at 235° (Found: N, 4.86. $C_{17}H_{11}O_4N$ requires N, 4.78 per cent.).

Acetylphenylacetylene and Cyanoacetamide.

The ketone, an yellow oil, b.p. 125-30°/ 15-18 mm., was obtained in about 25% yield.

3-Cyano-4-phenyl-6-methyl-2-pyridone (IV, R=Methyl).—That the reaction did not proceed very smoothly was evident from the fact that the reaction mixture became first red (as usual) and then instead of fading away (as recorded in the previous cases) became perceptibly brown as the reaction proceeded resulting in the separation of the sodium salt of the condensation product. It was, however, isolated as usual but the yield barely reached 40-50%. It resembled the other members of the series described, and crystallised from aqueous acetic acid in light yellow prismatic needles, m.p. 275-76°. An identical compound was also obtained when the condensation was carried out in the presence of Knoevenagel's reagents. The yield was very low, but was quite sufficient for the comparison. (Found: N, 13.58. $C_{13}H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 13.33 per cent.). It was further identified with a specimen from stock, as obtained from benzalacetone and cyanoacetamide.

The N-methyl derivative crystallised from methyl alcohol in nearly colourless needles, m.p. 146°, and resembled the other members of the series. Sen's compound (*vide supra*) also had an m.p. of 146°, and must have been identical with it. (Found: N, 12.73. $C_{14}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 12.50 per cent.).

Hydrolysis of the above Cyanopyridone: Formation of 4-Phenyl-6-methyl-2-hydroxypyridine (V, R=Methyl).—The compound was easily obtained by hydrolysing the original condensation product by 75% sulphuric acid (yield about 60%). It had all the properties of the hydroxypyridines described above. It was easily soluble in most solvents; crystallised from rectified spirit it was obtained in fine needles, m.p. 206-8°. (Found: N, 7.78. $C_{12}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 7.57 per cent.).

Acetylphenylacetylene and Ethyl Malonate.

Formation of Ethyl 4-Phenyl-6-methyl-2-pyrone-3-carboxylate.—The condensation was carried out in the usual way. The substance, crystallised from methyl alcohol in pale yellow plates, m. p. 92°. (Found: C, 69.14; H, 5.51. $C_{15}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 69.38; H, 5.42 per cent.). The ester when hydrolysed in the usual way gave rise to 4-phenyl-6-methyl-2-pyrone which resembled the previously described pyrone derivatives from *p*-toluylphenylacetylene etc. in all its properties and crystallised from alcohol in thin pale yellow plates, m.p. 185.86°. (Found: C, 77.18; H, 5.25. $C_{12}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 77.42; H, 5.38 per cent.).

Propionylphenylacetylene and Cyanoacetamide.

The ketone, prepared by the method of Moureau and Brachin, (*Compt. rend.*, 1903, 137, 795), is an yellow oil boiling at 115.20°/15 mm. (yield about 28%).

3-Cyano-4-phenyl-6-ethyl-2-pyridone (IV, R=Ethyl).—The reaction proceeded in an exactly similar way to the preceding case (yield about 40%). It resembled the other members in all respects. Crystallised from aqueous acetic acid it was obtained in pale yellow prismatic needles, m.p. 267.68°, (Bardhan recorded 260°) sintering and darkening a few degrees earlier. It was identified with a specimen obtained from the condensation of cyanoacetamide and α -methoxy- ω -propionylstyrene (Basu, *private communication*). (Found: N, 12.32. $C_{14}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 12.50 per cent.). The same compound was also obtained when the condensation was carried out in the presence of diethylamine or piperidine.

The *N*-methyl derivative crystallised from methyl alcohol in fine needles, melting at 153°, and resembled the other methyl derivatives described before. (Found: N, 11.93. $C_{15}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 11.76 per cent.).

Hydrolysis.—4-Phenyl-6-ethyl-2-hydroxypyridine (V, R=Ethyl).—The cyanopyridone was easily hydrolysed by 75% sulphuric acid. The hydroxypyridine separated only on neutralising the solution with sodium carbonate. It was very soluble in all common solvents, and resembled the other members of the series. Crystallised from 40% alcohol it was obtained in colourless needles, m.p. 165°. It was identified with other specimens of the hydroxypyridine from

other sources (*q.v.*) (Found: N, 7.04. $C_{13}H_{13}ON$ requires N, 7.04 per cent.).

Further work with esters of unsaturated acids is in progress, and will be shortly communicated.

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